

Academic Task Management and Learner's Development In Tagum City Division

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Abstract. This study explored the influence of academic task management on learners' development among 101 public junior high school teachers in Tagum City Division, Philippines. Guided by Bandura's Social Learning Theory and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, and adopted a quantitative descriptive-correlational method. Learners' development was evaluated in terms of their study habits, social skills, and behavior. The findings revealed that academic task management was consistently practiced at a high level across all domains. Correspondingly, learners exhibited strong development outcomes, with particular strength noted in social skills. The study confirmed a significant positive relationship between academic task management and learners' development, establishing that effective classroom strategies play a critical role in enhancing students' academic and personal growth. Among the examined dimensions of academic task management which were motivation to learn, classroom environment, and learners' participation, classroom environment emerged as the most influential factor in facilitating learners' development. The results stressed the importance of intentional, student-centered academic management in cultivating a supportive and empowering educational experience. This study aim to optimize instructional practices and create developmentally responsive learning environments. These insights may serve as a valuable reference for educators and policymakers in shaping evidence-based strategies that promote holistic learner development.

KEY WORDS

1. Academic task management
2. learners' development
3. classroom environment
4. learners' participation
5. Tagum City Division

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1. Introduction

One of a teacher's most essential roles is to organize classroom activities in such a way that they support student development. Genuine learning is difficult to achieve in a badly managed classroom with poorly taught lessons. Students of all abilities struggle to advance. Regardless of whether students are already performing well or are still catching up, a teacher's lack of order or clarity in managing academic tasks may keep them from reaching their full potential. In Nigeria, for example, the way teachers approach their academic task management facilitation of learners' development is somehow crucial with the drastic changes our educational system is facing nowadays. In other words, as teachers facilitating learners' development, is not a matter of choice but a necessity that teachers must urgently adopt in order to bridge the widening gap between the teachers' and the learners in terms of teachers' and learn-

ers' knowledge and skills (Senanu et al., 2019). In the province of Pampanga, the educational leaders aim to enhance educational outcomes and achieve academic success. However, significant challenges continue to obstruct these goals, particularly in the area of effective teaching and classroom management. A growing number of learners are failing to meet expected levels of academic proficiency and holistic development. Ericsson et al. (2019) emphasize that this ongoing problem is closely tied to deficiencies in teachers' academic task management and their ability to effectively facilitate learner growth. In Davao City, the inadequacy in Filipino learners' academic performance is partly linked to the improper and untimely management of academic tasks, as well as the ineffective facilitation of learner development by teachers. According to Douglas et al. (2021), learners often exhibit poor study habits, underdeveloped social skills, and behavioral problems, which contribute to academic underachievement, difficulty in building friendships, boredom, and a loss of self-confidence. These issues are seen as outcomes of insufficient academic task management and inappropriate teaching approaches by some educators. As noted by Martin and Bolliger (2019), research on academic task management and the facilitation of learners' development remains limited. The study conducted in Iloilo City revealed that there is still an existing problem in these areas, as many teachers continue to struggle with effectively managing academic tasks and facilitating meaningful learner development. These ongoing challenges highlight the need for improved strategies and targeted interventions to enhance classroom practices and learner outcomes. Santos et al. (2022) highlighted that poor academic task management and academic procrastination negatively affect students' academic performances and engagement. Supporting this, the study conducted in Tagum City revealed that these issues remain prevalent among Junior High School teachers.

Specifically, challenges in managing academic tasks and effectively supporting learner development continue to affect overall learner outcomes. The results of this study could assist public Junior High School teachers in identifying appropriate academic task management strategies and techniques that suit the diverse backgrounds of their learners. Furthermore, it highlights the academic task management variables that most influence learner improvement, offering insights for targeted interventions to address the persistent challenges in Tagum City Division.

1.1. Review of Related Literature—This section presents relevant literature discussing the relationship between teachers' academic task management and the holistic development of learners, focusing on motivation, classroom environment, participation, study habits, social skills, and behavior.

1.1.1. Academic Task Management—Academic task management refers to a teacher's ability to effectively plan, organize, and implement tasks that support learning. Raduan and Na (2020) and Crone et al. (2023) emphasize that effective task management allows teachers to prioritize meaningful instruction over routine responsibilities, directly influencing students' development. When teachers act as facilitators rather than mere transmitters of knowledge, they create a more engaging and productive learning environment (Gravett, 2019).

Poor task management leads to reduced instructional quality and wider achievement gaps (Sutherland, 2018). Conversely, when properly supported, teachers can foster improved motivation, classroom engagement, and the development of study habits and social behavior (Martin et al., 2018).

1.1.2. Motivation to Learn—Student motivation is a key driver of academic success. Washburn (2021) asserts that motivated students exhibit higher participation and engagement. Graham (2018) identifies five motivation influ-

encers: learner disposition, teacher role, content relevance, instructional strategies, and learning environment.

Van Dijk et al. (2020) highlight the role of teachers in designing stimulating, learner-centered environments. As students mature, intrinsic motivation guided by purpose becomes dominant (Knowles, 1984, as cited in Kiggundu, 2019), reinforcing the importance of guided academic tasking by teachers.

1.1.3. Classroom Environment—A well-structured, welcoming classroom positively impacts learning outcomes. Ahmad Choudhry (2019) and Vreekamp et al. (2023) stress that the physical and emotional environment must be inclusive, respectful, and learner-centered. When students participate in shaping their environment, they become more empowered and motivated (Abun et al., 2019).

1.1.4. Learners' Participation—Participation extends beyond attendance—it reflects confidence, preparedness, and engagement. Washburn (2021) and Creasey Knapcik (2018) argue that learners are more likely to engage when they feel capable and supported. Teachers play a critical role in identifying strategies that convert informal learning moments into formal development opportunities (Martin Bolliger, 2018; Muir et al., 2019).

1.1.5. Learners' Development—Facilitating learners' development involves guiding them to take ownership of their learning through goal-setting, resource utilization, and self-assessment (Ragusa Crampton, 2018). Muir et al. (2019) and De Bruijn (2021) emphasize that development is enhanced through active participation, purposeful learning, and reflective practices. Washburn's (2021) study in Australia confirms that teacher effectiveness is directly linked to measurable student growth.

1.1.6. Study Habits—Study habits are foundational to student success. Washburn (2021), Douglas (2021), and Gupta Chitkara (2018) find that students with effective study

practices show stronger self-efficacy and academic performance. Reinforcing these habits through structured support leads to better academic results and long-term success.

1.1.7. Social Skills—Social interaction among peers enhances learning. Senanu et al. (2019) and Kiggundu (2019) note that positive peer relationships encourage knowledge-sharing and behavioral modeling. Teachers must support the development of interpersonal skills to foster inclusive, cooperative learning environments (Razali et al., 2018; Kumar Aithal, 2019). Gravett (2019) links peer dynamics to academic orientation, especially in grouped or tracked settings.

1.1.8. Behavior—Behavioral development is essential for classroom harmony and student growth. Assigning meaningful tasks builds responsibility and trust (Thomas Thorpe, 2019; Ericsson et al., 2018). Self-worth and motivation emerge not from praise alone, but through authentic responsibility and achievement (Van Dijk et al., 2020; Ahmad Choudhry, 2019).

Linking Academic Task Management to Learners' Development Several studies affirm a strong relationship between academic task management and learners' cognitive, behavioral, and academic growth. Ahmad et al. (2019) show that structured guidance improves time management and performance. Ariarta et al. (2024) associate teacher planning with learner motivation and discipline, while Lourenço Paiva (2024) underscore the role of self-regulation and long-term planning in successful academic outcomes.

1.2. Synthesis—Learners' development facilitation through academic task management by teachers' is a challenge to find ways to improve the learners' potentials. It will also prepare the learners for a lifelong learning in a constantly changing society which hinges on the teachers' ability to do an appropriate academic tasking management skill. It is a known fact that learners' talents and skills must not be hidden like

buried treasures and it must not be left untapped. Only a teacher who was able to facilitate learners' development in the utmost way possible through appropriate academic task management can encourage learners to look for ways and knowledge to be competent and achieve success in today's world.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework— This study is anchored on Social Learning Theory (SLT) of Bandura (1997). According to Bandura's SLT, humans are dynamic processors of information and consider the relationship between their actions and its consequences. Humans here develop their social skills to interact and to learn through their relationship to others. Bandura's Social Learning Theory (SLT) put emphasis on the idea that cognitive and behavioral aspects are involved in the learners' learning processes. Through motivation, which could be through academic task management, learners knew how to identify an essential behavior that they would somehow imitate or apply on their learning process. It gives emphasis that people gain knowledge from one another, by means of observation, imitation, habits, and modeling. It affirms further that observational learning will not possibly take place unless cognitive processes will be utilized or make use of. These mental factors intervene in the learning process, which determines whether a new response is obtained or acquired. This study is also supported by Hierarchy of Needs Theory of Maslow (1954), which put emphasis that individual strives to seek higher needs when lower needs are fulfilled. According to Maslow, understanding workplace motivation requires a grasp of how human motivation is derived from needs that can be ranked in order of importance. Maslow's hierarchy of requirements identifies five primary needs. Basic psychological requirements, protection from external dangers, love

and affection and social connection, self-respect and esteem, and, lastly, self-realization and accomplishment are all examples of these needs. The motivations for initiating a behavior can be different from those that sustain it over time, as demonstrated by learner development in habits, social skills, and conduct. Even if the fundamental concepts remain the same, as the behavior becomes more consistent, their significance and influence frequently change. The environment has a big impact on behavior, and habits can be formed through encouragement and repetition. Social influences are also significant; the people in our lives can influence how simple or difficult it is for us to sustain new behaviors and can also define what is rewarding or attainable for us. Encouraged students are more inclined to stick with it. By watching others and taking in examples from their surroundings, toddlers also pick up a lot of information and abilities. Combining these metrics demonstrates how academic task management promotes cognitive development and academic success. Carefully organizing and carrying out assignments also helps create a positive learning environment that motivates students and cultivates a positive attitude toward learning. In summary, the connection between learner development and academic task management highlights the significance of a deliberate and well-structured teaching strategy that fosters students' whole growth in addition to their academic competency. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The independent variable which is the Academic Task Management. The indicators are Motivation to Learn, Classroom Environment, and Learner Participation. Meanwhile, the dependent variable is Learner's Development which were describe based on their Study habits, Social Skills, and Behavior.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

1.4. *Statement of the Problem*—This study aimed to explore how teachers manage academic tasks and how it relates to learners' development. In particular, it aimed to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the level of academic task management in terms of:
 - (1) motivation to learn;
 - (2) classroom environment;
 - (3) learners' participation?
- (2) What is the level of learners' development in terms of:
 - (1) study habits;
 - (2) social skills;
 - (3) behavior?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between academic task management and learners' development?
- (4) Which of the following academic task management domains has more influence to learners' development?

1.5. *Hypotheses*—The 0.05 level of significance is used to generate and test the following null hypothesis. Ho 1 There is no significant relationship between academic task management and learners' development. Ho 2 None of the academic task management domains significantly influence learners' development. Given the aforementioned problem scenario, the researcher feels that it is appropriate to recommend this investigation. The researcher expects that this analysis can help the educational sector's key sectors. The Department of Education (DepEd), legislators, school officials, educators, and students are all included in this.

Learners – The results of the study could

contribute to the enhancement of critical skills among learners. Academic task management is likely to emphasize activities that promote cognitive development, problem-solving, and analytical thinking, thereby preparing learners not only for academic success but also for life-long learning and adaptability. The following concepts were given operational definitions for a more thorough understanding:

Academic Task Management – Refers to the independent variable being described in this study using the following indicators: student participation, classroom environment, and motivation to learn. It reflects how teachers thoughtfully plan, organize, and carry out academics

tasks to create a meaningful and engaging learning experience for students.

Learner's Development – The dependent variable in this study is defined in terms of the following indicators: behavior, social skills, and study habits. It shows how pupils develop socially and personally in addition to intellectually.

This development can be seen in how they manage their time, interact with others, and show positive behavior inside and outside the classroom. It highlights the idea that learning is more than just grades, its about becoming better individuals ready to face life's challenges.

2. Methodology

This section covers the data collection procedure, data analysis, research instrument, research respondents, and research design.

2.1. Research Design—The study used a quantitative descriptive-correlational methodology to see how learners' development and academic work management were related. Formal, objective, and systematic, quantitative research collects knowledge about the world through numerical data. As stated by Sevilla et. al (2004), descriptive survey method deals with constructs based from indirect measures. The variables measured are not directly observable. This is a measure of association of variables with varying level of measurement. In certain cases, two variables become related because they are related to, or caused by another variable, hence, two variables generally tend to vary together; or the presence of one also indicates the presence of the other; or even one can be predicted from the presence of the other. Correlation method on the other hand, involves in identifying relationships between and among two variables (Guthrie Wigfield, 1999). It is in this light that the method is used; hence, the focal point of this research is to determine the relationship between strategic academic task management and facilitating learners' development.

2.2. Research Respondents—This survey was completed by 101 public junior high school teachers in Tagum City Division. Using strand as the foundation for stratification, the researcher used stratified random sample to choose individuals from purposively chosen

schools. Stratified random sampling is a type of probability sampling that allows researchers to boost precision compared to simple random sampling by splitting the population into non-overlapping groups, or strata, along a relevant dimension like gender (Salkind, 2020). Participants in this study were chosen based on certain inclusion criteria. The primary consideration was choosing participants who could provide data to support the study's goals. For the context of this study, public junior high school teachers in Tagum North District, Tagum City Division. Because it could supply the necessary data, the researcher chose to carry out the study at Tagum North, Tagum City Division. Therefore, the study's participants were limited to permanent public junior high school instructors who had three years of classroom experience and willingly signed the ICF. Furthermore, the investigation was restricted to the problem's nature as determined by the research questions.

2.3. Research Instrument—The chosen questionnaire from the classroom management self-assessment tool served as the study's instrument of Washburn revised edition (2021). The researcher enhanced the said questionnaire to draw-out sufficient information concerning the strategic academic task management and facilitating learners' development. Prior to the administration of the aforementioned instrument, the adviser reviewed the rough draft for adjustments

before it was provided to the panel of examiners and the group of experts for item validation. To confirm the validity of the questionnaire's contents, expert comments were appropriately taken into consideration and included into the final version of the instrument. It was tested to a group of high school teachers so that a reliability index will be obtained using Cronbach alpha. This is considered in order to get reliability of the questionnaire and to fit for the purpose it

is intended to serve in the study. The 5-Likert scale, which goes as follows: 5-Strongly Agree, 4-Agree, 3-Somewhat Agree, 2-Disagree, and 1-Strongly Disagree, was employed by the respondents to complete the questionnaire. The researcher used the variety of methods, descriptions, and interpretations listed below as a guide to assess the degree of academic work management:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	It means that the academic task management being described in this study is always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	High	It means that the academic task management being described in this study is oftentimes evident.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderate	It means that the academic task management being described in this study is sometimes evident.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	It means that the academic task management being described in this study is seldom evident.
1.00 - 1.79	Very Low	It means that the academic task management being described in this study is never evident.

The instrument's second section focused on the growth of the students. This survey was modified from the Washburn updated edition (2021), which included questions about behavior, social skills, and study habits. The respondents utilized the 5-Likert scale, which goes as follows: 5 = Strongly Agree, 4 = Agree,

3 = Somewhat Agree, 2 = Disagree, and 1 = Strongly Disagree, to answer the questions. The researcher employed a variety of methods, descriptions, and interpretations as shown below as a guide to assess the developmental stage of the learners:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Learners' development is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	High	Learners' development is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderate	Learners' development is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	Learners' development is seldom observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Very Low	Learners' development is never observed.

To guarantee the validity and reliability of the questionnaires, a panel of experts evaluated them after they had been improved through a pilot test. The experts' comments, including their recommendations and revisions, were included into the final versions.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—After the research questionnaire was validated, the researcher followed a series of steps to carry out the study. **Permission to Conduct the Study** – The researcher gained permission to conduct the investigation. The researcher received consent from the graduate school dean. The letter

of recommendation from the dean of the graduate school, was delivered with the authorization letters to the principals of the selected public secondary schools in Tagum North, Tagum City Division. The researcher delivered the letters to the principals of the schools where the study was carried out in person. The researcher initially showed up in the principal's office. The researcher distributed and collected the survey questionnaires after getting the go-ahead from the relevant offices.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire – After obtaining the participants' permission to carry out the study, the researcher next handed out the research instrument to each of the participants. Following the distribution of the questionnaires, the advantages of the survey were promptly discussed and elucidated to the individuals who had been identified as respondents to the study. At the same time, the researcher distributed the questionnaires in order to carry out the administration of the study. The participants in the study were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaires despite the fact that they were being tested. Following that, a quantitative analysis was performed on the data that had been acquired.

Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data – Following the retrieval of the questionnaires, the scores of all of the respondents were added together in order to organize the data in accordance with each indicator. In the subsequent step, SPSS was utilized to perform a descriptive and inferential analysis on each score.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher rapidly followed the processes that were considered to be required as the standard guidelines in order to carry out the research study in accordance with the study protocol assessment criteria. This was notably true when it came to the management of the population and the data. In order to do further analysis, the survey questionnaires along with the authors who provided support were submitted. After

receiving authorization from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the subsequent step of the investigation. **Informed Consent** – It was through the use of written informed permission that the researcher attempted to obtain the approval of the respondents. The participants were supplied with sufficient explanations to assist them in better comprehending the reasons why they were participating in the study, which enabled them to make an informed decision. They were also thoroughly informed about the aims of the investigation. The researcher emphasized that participation in the study was entirely voluntary. Respondents were not coerced in any way should they choose not to participate. Furthermore, the researcher took careful measures to safeguard the psychological well-being of all participants. **Informed written consent** was obtained from each respondent after clearly explaining that the purpose of the study was to examine the impact of strategic academic task management on facilitating learner development. **Vulnerability of Research Participants** – Due to the fact that all of the individuals who took part in the research were of legal age and employed as teachers of junior high school students in public schools, they were not considered to be susceptible. However, it is possible that they are still considered to be psychologically weak. It was emphasized by the researcher that the survey would be carried out at a time that was most suitable for the individuals who participated. In addition, the researcher ensured that the confidentiality of any and all material that was disclosed. **Privacy and Confidentiality** – According to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher made certain that the data could not be traced to the participants who were the actual source of the information. This was done in order to ensure that the respondents' identities were protected. In addition, the researcher guaranteed that every single piece of personal information pertaining to the respondents would be kept confidential without their consent. The

researcher was the only one who had access to the information in order to ensure that no private information would be disclosed whatsoever. In order to ensure that the respondents' privacy was not compromised, it was made certain that the researcher was the only individual who had access to the survey data. After the necessary data have been gathered, the researcher will proceed forward. For the purpose of ensuring that the respondents who were the true source of the data could not be identified, the survey findings were disposed of in a manner that guaranteed their permanent destruction. Risk, Benefits and Safety – As part of the process of administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher provided the respondents with complete and accurate information regarding the nature of their involvement. Additionally, the researcher provided a comprehensive and appropriate explanation of the objectives and advantages of the study, as well as the confidentiality of their responses, as indicated in the online survey questionnaire. Subjects who participated in the study were given the opportunity to ask questions that were relevant to the investigation. In addition, the researcher made certain that the individuals who participated in the study were not put in any hazardous situations in any way. Furthermore, neither the questionnaire nor the interview guide that were utilized in this research project had any statements that were demeaning or unacceptable to the individuals who participated in the research for the purpose of this study. Similarly, the purpose of this study is just to collect academic information that is relevant to the study, and participants were not asked to provide any personal information by the researchers. In order to minimize any potential difficulties, the researcher made certain that the respondents were provided with sufficient time to finish answering the survey questions. If the respondents felt that they were unable to address the material that was being requested of them, they had the option to decline to par-

ticipate in the study. Additionally, they had the freedom to refuse to answer any questions that caused them to experience psychological or emotional distress. Justice – To guarantee that the selection of participants was conducted in a fair manner, the researcher treated all possible respondents in the same manner, without showing any partiality or bias. The selection process was primarily based on complying with the requirements, which included being a permanent public junior high school teacher in the schools that were identified. In the course of the data collecting process, the researcher took great care to avoid interfering with the respondents' typical routines and made every attempt to show respect for the time they had available. Each individual who took part in the event was presented with a modest token of appreciation, which consisted of objects that may be kept as souvenirs. These were sent by courier after being thoughtfully wrapped and delivered. Transparency – All of the communications that were associated with the research were carried out in an open and honest manner in order to guarantee transparency throughout the entire investigation. All of the participants' health and safety were the primary concerns of the researcher as they meticulously adhered to the protocols that were specified for this study. The conclusions were supported by the inclusion of the appropriate supporting papers that were utilized in the data analysis. In addition, the researcher ensured that they maintained objectivity throughout the process of evaluating the data and presenting the findings, and they provided a clear explanation of how the participants were involved. Qualification of the Researcher – It was the responsibility of the researcher to ensure that the responses of the respondents were not influenced by any extraneous circumstances, such as conflicts of interest. Under the condition that they adhered to the appropriate protocols in order to protect the respondents' privacy, the information would be made accessi-

ble, which would enable the respondents as well as the school administrators of the schools that participated in the study to view the findings of the research. The Division of Tagum City will be given a copy of the findings of the research so that the individuals who participated in the study can have access to them and make use of them for various purposes, including education and future research. In addition, the researcher expressed gratitude to all of those individuals who contributed to the accomplishment of the study. Adequacy of Facilities – In order to complete the study within the window of time that was allocated, the researcher made sure that the respondents were in a comfortable environment and that there was an abundance of learning tools that were easily accessible. The researcher was able to ensure that the data collected from the respondents was accurate and that errors in encoding were avoided by accurately encoding the evaluations of the respondents throughout the day, when the researcher was not too weary to complete the assessments. Furthermore, both the analysis and the outcomes that were acquired were competent and consistent, which is the primary foundation for sufficiency.

Community Involvement – A prudent option would have been to involve the community in each and every level of the research process, from the planning stage to the reporting stage. As a consequence of this, the researcher had the intention of disseminating the findings to the community, and the participation of the community was at the forefront of the decision-

making process on the study objective, the most appropriate strategy to implement in their circumstances, and the manner in which to apply the findings. After then, the findings of the study would be disseminated to the community through various gatherings, including conferences, forums, and get-togethers.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were employed by the researcher to analyze and interpret the collected data in a systematic and objective manner: Weighted Mean – Utilizing the weighted mean, an evaluation was carried out to determine the extent to which students were making progress and the overall level of academic task management strategies among teachers. It made it possible for the researcher to recognize patterns and evaluate the average levels of perception held by the respondents with regard to a variety of variables. Pearson’s Correlation – For the purpose of determining the intensity and direction of the association between teachers’ ability to manage academic tasks and the growth of their students, Pearson’s correlation coefficient was utilized. There was a substantial linear correlation between the two variables, and this statistical test was helpful in determining whether or not it existed. Regression – The degree to which responders’ academic work management affected students’ progress was estimated using regression analysis. Through this method, the researcher was able to identify which aspects of task management served as predictors of learner outcomes.

3. Results and Discussion

It was in this chapter that the results of this study were reported. A comprehensive discussion, analysis, and interpretation of them was carried out.

3.1. *Level of Academic Task Management*—The level of academic task management refers to how effectively students organize, prioritize, and complete their academic responsibil-

ities. It plays a crucial role in academic success, as strong task management skills help students meet deadlines, reduce stress, and improve overall performance. Understanding and improv-

ing these skills can lead to more efficient study habits and better learning outcomes.

3.1.1. Motivation to Learn—The statistics about the level of academic task management in terms of motivation to learn were reported in Table 1. The presentation is focused on the highest, middle, and lowest mean ratings obtained: The item 1 has the highest mean, with the statement, “The teacher manages learners’ attention to the teaching-learning process.” (4.35); While the item with the median rating is the item 7, with the statement, “The teacher manages learners’ interests to learn and value more their education.” (4.08); and the item with the lowest mean rating is item 5, with the statement, “The teacher manages learners’ eagerness to work with their co-learners.” (3.79). This has gained an overall mean rating of 4.11, indicating that the level of academic task management in terms of motivation to learn is oftentimes evident. The findings indicate that academic task management in the context of motivation to learn is generally strong and well-practiced by teachers. Learners are effectively guided to stay attentive and engaged during the teaching-learning process, which reflects a high degree of instructional control and learner focus. This level of motivation management suggests that educators are aware of the importance of sustaining student interest and directing attention as a core component of ef-

Likewise, Van Dijk et al. (2020) accentuated the psychological importance of safe, accessible, and personalized learning spaces in sustaining internal motivation. The study mirrors this, with teachers rated highly for encouraging a positive attitude and commitment to learning. Similarly, Kiggundu (2019) stressed that as learners mature, internal motivation becomes a primary driver of academic behavior. The teacher’s role in cultivating these internal values through task management, as seen in this study, confirms his assertion. Additionally, Martin and

fective learning. Overall, the implementation of strategies to motivate learners appears to be consistent and positively received in the classroom environment. However, the results also highlight some variation in how motivation is fostered across different areas. While learners’ attention and interest are managed effectively, their eagerness to engage collaboratively with peers is comparatively less emphasized. This suggests a potential gap in promoting teamwork and cooperative learning within motivational strategies. Enhancing these aspects could contribute to a more holistic approach to motivation, ensuring that both individual engagement and collaborative enthusiasm are equally nurtured in the learning process. The findings of the study supports Washburn (2021), who emphasized that learners exhibit high engagement when motivated by well-managed academic routines. His framework identifies attentiveness, persistence, and eagerness as behavioral outcomes of strong motivation strategies where teachers effectively inspired learners’ focus and dedication. Also, Graham (2018) outlined the five components of learner motivation: teacher influence, student interest, relevant content, instructional strategy, and a supportive environment. The alignment between these elements and the study’s findings reinforces that teacher-led motivation fosters a proactive learning attitude among students.

Bolliger (2018) emphasized the connection between learner-centered strategies and increased motivation. The study’s results, which showed strong learner interest and enthusiasm reflect the effectiveness of personalized and participative teaching practices.

3.1.2. Classroom Environment—The information regarding the level of academic work management in relation to the classroom environment is presented in Table 2. The presentation concentrates on the indicators with the rating obtained from highest, median and the

Table 1. The Level of Academic Task Management in Terms of Motivation to Learn

No.	Statement	Mean
1	The teacher manages learners' attention to the teaching-learning process.	4.35
2	The teacher manages learners' flexibility/ openness to learn new knowledge and ideas.	4.29
3	The teacher manages learners' inspiration to take part in the classroom activities.	4.17
4	The teacher manages learners' motivation to adapt to changes and new approaches to learning.	4.10
5	The teacher manages learners' eagerness to work with their co-learners.	3.79
6	The teacher manages learners' dedication to begin working on tasks immediately.	3.95
7	The teacher manages learners' interests to learn and value more their education.	4.08
8	The teacher manages learners' to manifest positive attitude in dealing with the subject and other related tasks.	4.17
9	The teacher manages learners' to be enthusiastic and to carry out assigned tasks and responsibilities appropriately.	4.11
10	The teacher manages learners' to be patient and persistent in dealing with the task.	4.11
Overall Mean		4.11

least: item 9, with the statement, “The teacher manages learners’ opportunities to express their opinions and ideas.” has the highest mean rating of 4.31. While the item 2, “The teacher manages learners’ ideas in structuring the classroom.”, has the median rating, (4.11). The item 3 and 4, with the statements, “The teacher manages learners’ interaction and ensure its quality and positivity.” and “The teacher manages learners’ involvement in the process of creating their environment.” both have the mean rating of 4.07 have the lowest mean rating. A mean score of 4.17 for the entire group, which is equivalent to the descriptive term “high” indicates that academic task management in terms of classroom environment is oftentimes evident. The study reveals that the academic task management practiced by teachers in shaping the classroom environment is consistently evident and positively perceived. Teachers are notably effective in fostering an open atmosphere where learners feel encouraged to voice their opin-

ions and contribute their ideas. This reflects a learning environment that values student expression and supports active engagement in classroom dynamics. The ability of educators to create such spaces plays a vital role in enhancing learners’ sense of belonging and participation. Nevertheless, the results suggest areas where classroom environment management could be strengthened. In particular, more emphasis may be needed in facilitating quality interactions among learners and involving them more deeply in shaping their immediate learning environment. These aspects, though still present, may benefit from targeted strategies that promote collaborative and inclusive classroom experiences. Addressing these gaps can lead to more meaningful learner engagement, improved academic outcomes, and a more supportive and dynamic classroom climate. The result of the study agrees with Vreekamp et al. (2023) advocated for classrooms that promote interaction, emotional security, and learner participate dy-

dynamic and responsive learning spaces that cater to diverse learner needs. These qualities were central to the study’s findings, with teachers being rated highly for fostering openness and equality in the classroom.

Table 2. The Level of Academic Task Management in Terms of Classroom Environment

No.	Statement	Mean
1	The teacher manages learners’ effort in all activities that they do.	4.21
2	The teacher manages learners’ ideas in structuring the classroom.	4.11
3	The teacher manages learners’ interaction and ensures its quality and positivity.	4.07
4	The teacher manages learners’ involvement in the process of creating their environment.	4.07
5	The teacher manages learners’ feeling of having a classroom community.	4.10
6	The teacher manages learners’ sense of empowerment and involvement in establishing rules.	4.08
7	The teacher manages learners’ to be organized and innovative.	4.29
8	The teacher manages learners’ opportunities to express their opinions and ideas.	4.30
9	The teacher manages learners’ to allow equal interactions and collaboration.	4.31
10	The teacher manages learners’ to place a strong emphasis on an interactive classroom environment.	4.18
Overall Mean		4.17

Moreover, Abun et al. (2019) emphasized how involving learners in shaping their learning space enhances motivation and ownership. This is directly supported by the study’s finding that students were encouraged to express opinions and structure their environment. Further, Crone et al. (2023) found that the physical and emotional layout of classrooms significantly influences learner participation and trust. This correlates with the study’s strong ratings on classroom management and shared rule-making. Furthermore, Kumar and Aithal (2019) argued that structured and innovative environments support both cognitive and social engagement. The indicators in this study, such as community-building and innovation, validate their claims. Nevertheless, Martin et al. (2019) stressed that learner involvement in classroom management improves

both behavioral and academic outcomes. The study supports this with high scores in learner empowerment and collaboration.

3.1.3. Learners’ Participation—The information about the degree of academic task management in terms of the learners’ participation is organized and presented in Table 3. The presentation is logically arranged from the highest, median rating to the lowest obtained, namely: item 1, “The teacher manages learners’ awareness of the potential differences in expectations for participation.” has the highest mean rating of 4.21. The item 5, “The teacher manages learners’ meaningful construction of knowledge.” has the median rating of 4.05; The item 7, “The teacher manages learners’ ease to transition from one activity to another.” (3.98) has the lowest mean rating. In this particular indicator, the only item

that has a descriptive equivalent of "Very High" is the one that has the highest mean rating. The rest of the 9 items have a descriptive equivalent of "High". Collectively, this has gained an Overall Mean of 4.08 with a descriptive equivalent of "High", which indicates oftentimes evident. The findings demonstrate that teachers exhibit a strong level of academic task management in promoting learners' participation, which is reflected in the consistent "High" ratings across most indicators. Notably, learners are well-guided in understanding the expectations surrounding their participation, suggesting that clarity and direction are effectively communicated in the classroom. This contributes to the development of learners who are self-assured, engaged, and aware of their roles within the learning process. Students are encouraged to actively participate in the construction of knowledge and to contribute to classroom debates through the focus placed on participation. Despite the overall positive results, there is a slight indication that transitioning between activities is managed with comparatively less effectiveness. While participation is encouraged, ensur-

Also, Muir et al. (2019) emphasized that meaningful participation connects academic learning with personal and social growth. The teacher strategies in this study, fostering experiential, hands-on tasks align with this perspective. Likewise, Martin and Bolliger (2018) reinforced that participatory learning improves both cognitive and emotional engagement. The consistently high indicators for learner involvement in this study mirror their findings.

3.2. *Summary of The Level of Academic Task Management*—Presented in Table 4 are data on the Summary of the Level of Academic Task Management. The Overall Mean of 4.12, which is "High" and oftentimes evident, is distributed by the indicators. They were presented with the corresponding mean as follows: moti-

ing smooth and efficient shifts from one task to another appears to be a relative area of improvement. Enhancing this aspect can lead to better learning continuity and reduce disruptions that may affect engagement. Strengthening transitions, along with sustaining participation strategies, will help create a more seamless and responsive learning environment. The findings of the study aligns with the study of Creasey and Knapcik (2019), who described participation as emerging from learners' clarity on expectations and freedom to engage. Teachers in the study were rated highly for creating such clarity and responsiveness. In addition, Hewson (2018) highlighted that learners engage better when they feel they can succeed. The study reflects this with strong ratings on participation and learner initiative, especially when tasks are clearly managed. Also, Muir et al. (2019) emphasized that meaningful participation connects academic learning with personal and social growth. The teacher strategies in this study are fostering experiential, hands-on tasks align with this perspective.

vation to learn (4.11), classroom environment (4.17), and learners' participation (4.08). All of these indicators have descriptive equivalents of "High". The result of the data on the level of academic task management reveals a consistently strong and favorable perception across all indicators. The summary of the results highlights a consistently positive level of academic task management across all assessed indicators. Teachers are perceived to effectively manage learners' motivation, create conducive classroom environments, and encourage active participation. This consistency suggests that the foundational elements of academic engagement are being addressed in a balanced and integrated manner. The favorable perception across indicators reflects a well-rounded approach in facilitating

Table 3. The Level of Academic Task Management in Terms of Classroom Environment

No.	Statement	Mean
1	The teacher manages learners' effort in all activities that they do.	4.21
2	The teacher manages learners' ideas in structuring the classroom.	4.11
3	The teacher manages learners' interaction and ensures its quality and positivity.	4.07
4	The teacher manages learners' involvement in the process of creating their environment.	4.07
5	The teacher manages learners' feeling of having a classroom community.	4.10
6	The teacher manages learners' sense of empowerment and involvement in establishing rules.	4.08
7	The teacher manages learners' to be organized and innovative.	4.29
8	The teacher manages learners' opportunities to express their opinions and ideas.	4.30
9	The teacher manages learners' to allow equal interactions and collaboration.	4.31
10	The teacher manages learners' to place a strong emphasis on an interactive classroom environment.	4.18
Overall Mean		4.17

productive learning experiences. The alignment in performance across motivation, environment, and participation underscores a comprehensive strategy in managing academic tasks. Educators appear to maintain effective practices that support both individual learner needs and the collective classroom dynamic. This integrated approach not only enhances learning outcomes but also promotes sustained engagement and development. Overall, the findings affirm the strength of current teaching strategies in fostering an effective academic environment. The

study's findings agrees with Crone et al. (2023), as they identified synergy between motivation, structured classroom environments, and learner participation as key to academic success. The evenly high scores across domains in this study reflect that comprehensive approach. Similarly, Gravett (2019) argued for facilitative teaching methods that integrate these three components to boost learning outcomes. This study confirms her framework, showing cohesive results across task management areas.

Raduan and Na (2020) emphasized providing strategic support across motivation, organization, and engagement. This supports the

study's conclusion that teachers balanced these areas effectively to promote learning. Moreover, Graham (2019) illustrated the importance

Table 4. Summary of The Level of Academic Task Management

Indicators	Mean
Motivation to Learn	4.11
Classroom Environment	4.17
Learners' Participation	4.08
Overall Mean	4.12

of interconnected classroom factors in building sustained engagement. The study's strong mean scores across motivation, environment, and participation validate this model. Also, Martin et al. (2019) confirmed that structured academic environments depend on simultaneous focus on task relevance, teacher support, and student involvement, all of which were highly evident in this study.

3.3. *The Level of Learners' Development*—The level of learners' development in terms of study habits reflects how well students have cultivated effective and consistent learning routines. Strong study habits are essential for academic achievement, as they influence concentration, time management, and information retention. Assessing this development helps educators identify areas where support may be needed to enhance students' learning strategies and academic growth.

3.3.1. *Study Habits*—The information regarding the level of development of learners in terms of their study habits is presented in Table 5. The presentation was focused on the highest, median and the lowest mean ratings obtained: item 5, "The teacher facilitates learners' to express questions about difficult concepts in order to understand them better." and item 9 "The teacher facilitates learners' confidence in working with challenging tasks.", both have the highest mean rating of 4.03; while the item 3, with the statement, "The teacher facilitates learners' up-to-date submission of projects and homeworks.", has the median rating of 3.89; The items 7 and 10, with the statements, "The teacher facilitates learners' study time with a

group.", and "The teacher facilitates learners' persistence to avoid cramming.", respectively both have the lowest mean rating of 3.79 among the 10 items. This has gained an overall mean rating of 3.92, indicating that the level of learners' development in terms of study habits, is oftentimes evident. All items in this indicator have "High" descriptive ratings. Further, The results show that, thanks to their teachers, students typically exhibit a significant degree of progress in their study habits. Learners show strength in expressing questions for better understanding and in facing challenging academic tasks with confidence. These aspects reflect the effectiveness of teachers in nurturing critical thinking and resilience among students. The consistent high ratings across items affirm that supportive study behaviors are being actively encouraged in the classroom. However, the data also point to areas that may need greater emphasis, particularly in collaborative study efforts and time management. While learners benefit from guided questioning and confidence-building, the habits of group study and avoiding last-minute cramming appear to be less developed. This suggests a potential gap in fostering peer collaboration and long-term planning strategies. Addressing these aspects could lead to more balanced and self-directed study practices among learners. The results of the study's findings supports Washburn (2021), who highlighted that effective study habits like time management, persistence, and question-asking are cultivated through consistent teacher support. The study reflects this, with learners scoring high in these very areas. Also, it agrees with

the assumption of Douglas (2021) that linked self-efficacy with productive study routines, noting that learners with confidence often manage time and academic pressure more effectively. The results from this study confirm that learners demonstrated strong goal-setting and focus. As well, Gupta and Chitkara (2019) highlighted that structured study behaviors, including consistent attendance and timely submission of academic tasks, are strongly linked to learners' academic success. These habits help learners stay organized, meet academic expectations, and actively engage in the learning process. In alignment with this, the present study revealed high ratings in these areas, indicating that such behaviors are positively practiced and contribute

to learner performance. Nevertheless, Crone et al. (2023) found that continuous reinforcement of academic routines significantly contributes to long-term improvements in learners' behavior and persistence in academic tasks. Their research suggests that habitual support and guidance can lead to more independent and self-regulated learners over time. The current study echoes this insight, as it observed consistent learner habits that reflect sustained behavioral discipline and academic resilience. In addition, Gravett (2019) noted that when teachers facilitate reflection and ownership over learning, study habits improve. The high ratings for self-directed study goals in this study affirm that relationship.

Table 5. The Level of Learners' Development in Terms of Study Habits

No.	Statement	Mean
1	The teacher facilitates learners' to stick to a study schedule and achieve study goals.	3.96
2	The teacher facilitates learners' regular attendance in class.	3.90
3	The teacher facilitates learners' up-to-date submission of projects and homeworks.	3.89
4	The teacher facilitates learners' taking down notes during class lectures.	3.80
5	The teacher facilitates learners' to express questions about difficult concepts in order to understand them better.	4.03
6	The teacher facilitates learners' interest to get the meaning of new words.	4.01
7	The teacher facilitates learners' study time with a group.	3.79
8	The teacher facilitates learners' setting of standards for himself/herself.	3.97
9	The teacher facilitates learners' confidence in working with challenging tasks.	4.03
10	The teacher facilitates learners' persistence to avoid cramming.	3.79
Overall Mean		3.92

3.3.2. *Social Skills*—Table 6 presents the data on the social skills development level of learners, emphasizing the particular characteristics sorted from highest to lowest based on mean scores. The highest-rated item, is item 3 with a mean of 4.39, indicates that “The teacher facil-

itates learners' to enjoy working with their co-learners.” Following is the item 2, with the statement, “The teacher facilitates learners' to show willingness to participate/join in team building activities.”, receiving a median mean rating of 4.17. The item that received the lowest mean rat-

ing of 4.11, has the statement, “The teacher facilitates learners’ to be compassionate and cooperative rather than suspicious and antagonistic towards others.” With a descriptive equivalent of ‘Very High,’ the overall mean of 4.24 shows that the degree of social skill development of the students is consistently apparent. Moreover, the results demonstrate that learners exhibit a highly developed level of social skills, consistently supported by their teachers through collaborative and interactive learning experiences. Students are especially encouraged to enjoy working with peers, which suggests a classroom culture that values cooperation and team spirit. This reflects the teachers’ effectiveness in promoting environments where positive social interactions thrive. The consistently strong performance across indicators points to a learning setting that fosters respectful and meaningful peer relationships. Although the ratings are uniformly high, there is slightly less emphasis on nurturing compassion and cooperative attitudes over negative social tendencies. While still evident, this suggests an opportunity to reinforce emotional intelligence and empathy among learners. Improving this element could lessen the likelihood of interpersonal disputes and improve the classroom’s general social atmosphere. Such development would complement the existing strengths in collaboration and group participation, resulting in more well-rounded social growth. The findings of the study aligns as well with Senanu et al. (2019), which asserted that peer interaction

and cooperation directly impact academic outcomes and classroom engagement. The study reflects this, with learners showing high levels of collaboration and relationship-building. Also, Kiggundu (2019) emphasized that learners are more likely to exhibit positive behaviors when they feel that their efforts and contributions are valued within the learning environment. When learners see that their input makes a difference, they become more engaged and motivated to participate. This aligns with the present study’s findings, where learners showed active involvement in group tasks and expressed genuine satisfaction in collaborating with their peers. Kumar and Aithal (2019), explained that learners who consistently follow assigned roles and exercise self-control are more likely to develop essential social skills. Such behaviors foster mutual respect, accountability, and constructive peer interactions. The current study reflected this assertion, as learners were observed to fulfill responsibilities effectively and exhibit emotional regulation in social settings. While, Razali et al. (2018) argued that social competence plays a vital role in supporting learners’ academic growth and success. Traits such as empathy, self-discipline, and the ability to positively influence others are seen as critical to building strong academic and interpersonal foundations. This is evident in the study, where learners displayed compassion, maintained discipline, and were able to lead or inspire peers within collaborative learning contexts.

Moreover, Martin and Bolliger (2018) emphasized the importance of collaborative structures in supporting learner interaction. The study affirms this, with learners displaying high levels of teamwork and empathy.

3.3.3. Behavior—Table 7 showed the data on the level of Learners’ Development in terms of Behavior, with the indicators arranged from highest, median to lowest mean ratings. The

highest-rated item, is item 1, with the statement, “The teacher facilitates learners’ belief in their capacity to execute behaviors necessary to produce beneficial learning.”, received a mean of 4.38. This was followed by the item 6, having the median rating of 4.08, with the statement, “The teacher facilitates learners’ to show confidence in dealing with my social environment.” The item 2, with the statement, “The teacher

Table 6. The Level of Learners’ Development in Terms of Social Skills

No.	Statement	Mean
1	The teacher facilitates learners’ to get along with others.	4.23
2	The teacher facilitates learners’ to show willingness to participate/join in team building activities.	4.17
3	The teacher facilitates learners’ to enjoy working with their co-learners.	4.39
4	The teacher facilitates learners’ to maintain good relationship with co-learners.	4.23
5	The teacher facilitates learners’ to influence co-learners’ classroom performance and learning outcomes in positive ways.	4.29
6	The teacher facilitates learners’ to have the capacity to adhere to the roles appropriate during the learning process.	4.15
7	The teacher facilitates learners’ to encourage other learners to participate in group task.	4.30
8	The teacher facilitates learners’ to be compassionate and cooperative rather than suspicious and antagonistic towards others.	4.11
9	The teacher facilitates learners’ to show self-discipline, act dutifully and aim for achievement.	4.25
10	The teacher facilitates learners’ to demonstrate rapport with co-learners.	4.25
Overall Mean		4.24

facilitates learners’ confidence in their ability to exert control over their own behavior.” has the lowest mean rating of 3.94. There were 5 indicators that were rated with a descriptive equivalent of “Very High”, and the other 5 items were rated with a descriptive equivalent of “High”, resulting in an Overall Mean of 4.17. The findings reflect a strong level of learners’ behavioral development, supported by teachers who effectively foster positive self-beliefs and productive actions. Learners are particularly confident in their ability to engage in behaviors that lead to meaningful learning outcomes, indicating a well-established foundation of academic self-efficacy. This demonstrates the success of teaching strategies that emphasize personal responsibility and the development of goal-directed behavior. The high ratings across several indicators underscore a learning environment that encourages learners to act with purpose and persistence. Despite the overall positive results, the data suggests that learners show slightly less

confidence in regulating their own behavior independently. This indicates that while external guidance is effective, some students may still be developing internal behavioral control. Teachers may need to strengthen interventions that promote self-discipline and self-regulation as personal competencies. Addressing this will help learners become more autonomous and resilient in managing their actions both within and beyond the classroom. The findings of the study aligns with the findings of Thomas and Thorpe (2019) emphasized that assigning meaningful responsibilities transforms learner behavior and promotes intrinsic control. The high behavioral engagement in this study reflects their model. Somehow, Ericsson et al. (2018) showed that learners’ belief in their capabilities leads to improved behavior and task performance. This study affirms those claims, especially through ratings on confidence and perseverance. Additionally, Van Dijk et al. (2020) highlighted that true behavioral change emerges through

challenges and accountability. Learners in the study demonstrated mature coping abilities and discipline, in line with this idea. The study also affirms the study of Ahmad et al. (2019), who described how structure and predictability help shape learners' behavioral responses. The results of this study show that learners main-

tained appropriate behavior within a structured environment. Likewise, Martin et al. (2018) found that behavior improves when learners are viewed as capable and entrusted with autonomy. This is reflected in the study's indicators related to ownership and positive behavior regulation.

Table 7. The Level of Learners' Development in Terms of Behavior

No.	Statement	Mean
1	The teacher facilitates learners' belief in their capacity to execute behaviors necessary to produce beneficial learning.	4.38
2	The teacher facilitates learners' confidence in their ability to exert control over their own behavior.	3.94
3	The teacher facilitates learners' belief in their capability to apply actions necessary for productive learning.	4.14
4	The teacher facilitates learners' to remain calm when facing difficulties because they can rely on their coping abilities.	4.24
5	The teacher facilitates learners' to be confident that they could deal efficiently with unexpected events/unforeseen situations.	4.24
6	The teacher facilitates learners' to show confidence in dealing with my social environment.	4.08
7	The teacher facilitates learners' to observe appropriate behavior to attain efficiency in their tasks.	4.36
8	The teacher facilitates learners' to try hard enough to manage and solve difficult problems.	4.04
9	The teacher facilitates learners' to exert effort in all tasks given to them.	4.21
10	The teacher facilitates learners' to feel useful and pre-occupied with worthwhile activities rather than misbehaving.	4.05
Overall Mean		4.17

3.4. *Summary of the Level of Learners' Development*—Table 8 showed the data on the Summary of the Level of Learners' Development. The data in this table are presented with the corresponding means: study habits (3.92), social skills (4.24), and behavior (4.17). Only 1 indicator out of the three has a descriptive equivalent of "Very High", and the remaining two indicators have "High" descriptive equivalent. The Overall Mean resulting to 4.11, has a "High" descriptive equivalent, indicates that the level of learners' development was oftentimes evident in the three indicators. Furthermore, the sum-

mary of the results reveals that learners demonstrate a consistently strong level of development across study habits, social skills, and behavior. Among these areas, social skills emerged as the most prominent strength, suggesting that learners are highly engaged in interpersonal interactions and cooperative learning. This indicates that teachers are particularly effective in fostering environments where communication and collaboration are actively promoted. The overall results reflect a well-rounded development pattern, with learners showing readiness in both academic and social domains. However, while

all areas of development were rated positively, study habits showed relatively less prominence compared to the other indicators. This implies that learners may benefit from additional support in establishing routines, time management, and self-directed learning strategies. Enhancing these habits can help improve academic consistency and independent performance. Overall, the findings point to a favorable developmental landscape with opportunities for targeted growth in academic discipline. The results gath-

ered affirms Raduan and Na (2020) which stated that student development is multi-dimensional, combining academic discipline, emotional intelligence, and social interaction. The high scores across all domains in this study reflect that integrative model. Nevertheless, Douglas et al. (2021) asserted that facilitative strategies improve student outcomes holistically. This aligns with the study’s consistent positive results in study habits, behavior, and social skills.

Table 8. Summary of The Level of Learners’ Development

Indicators	Mean
Study Habits	3.92
Social Skills	4.24
Behavior	4.17
Overall Mean	4.11

It was also affirmed by the findings of the study that Muir et al. (2019) emphasized the link between identity, participation, and social learning. The study supports this, with students showing development across self-control, teamwork, and persistence. Further, Van Dijk et al. (2020) found that personal responsibility is cultivated when learners are supported across multiple domains. The study’s findings confirm that learners demonstrated self-efficacy and collaborative competence. Furthermore, Gravett (2019) promoted an integrated teaching approach that fosters personal and academic growth. The study validates this, with strong results across all areas of learner development.

3.5. *Relationship Between Academic Task Management and Learners’ Development*—Table 9 presented the data on the significant relationship between academic task management and learners’ development in public elementary schools, as measured by Pearson’s r. The calculated r-value of 0.794 suggests a significant or high degree of association. The null hypothesis is rejected at the significance level

since the p-value of 0.00 is smaller than the alpha value of 0.05. Both the independent and dependent variables are statistically significant, according to the results. Hence, there was a significant relationship between academic task management and learners’ development. The result indicates a high positive correlation ($r = 0.794$) between academic task management and learners’ development, with a p-value of 0.00, suggesting the relationship is statistically significant. This means that as the level of academic task management improves, there is a consistent increase in learners’ development across areas such as study habits, social skills, and behavior. The strength of this correlation highlights how crucial task management strategies are in promoting comprehensive learner growth. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming a significant relationship between the variables. A key component of academic achievement is motivation to learn, which has a direct impact on a student’s involvement and perseverance. The results of the analysis show a statistically significant and substantial positive association

between students' motivation and academic task management, with a high Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.794$) and a p-value of 0.00. When educators implement well-organized and structured academic tasks, learners are more likely to feel competent and autonomous in their educational pursuits. This sense of control fosters intrinsic motivation, which in turn promotes sustained academic effort and interest. Through strategies such as clear goal-setting, timely feedback, and appropriate task difficulty, academic task management enhances students' willingness to engage with content, overcome challenges, and achieve academic goals. Consequently, the findings underscore the pivotal role that effective task management plays in cultivating learners' motivation, thereby contributing significantly to their overall development. The classroom environment serves as a critical context in which learners' cognitive, emotional, and social development occurs. With a p-value of 0.00 and a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.794, the study's results show a strong and positive link between academic task management and classroom environment quality. Students are more likely to view the classroom as secure, orderly, and encouraging when academic assignments are handled methodically and are marked by clarity, consistency, and fairness. This structured environment minimizes disruptions and enhances focus, allowing learners to engage meaningfully with the content and with their peers. A well-managed classroom fosters positive interactions, reduces stress and confusion, and builds a sense of community. These conditions collectively support emotional well-being and academic achievement, both of which are integral to holistic learner development. Thus, effective academic task management contributes not only to academic outcomes but also to the establishment of a conducive learning environment. Learners' participation reflects their active engagement in classroom activities, discussions, and academic responsibilities. The statistical analysis indicates a high correlation ($r = 0.794$) and a p-value of 0.00, demonstrating a significant and robust relationship between academic task management and the level of student participation. When tasks are well-managed through clear instructions, inclusive group work, and active learning strategies, students are more inclined to involve themselves in the learning process. This active participation promotes skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, and communication, which are essential for comprehensive learner development. Moreover, participation reinforces a sense of agency and responsibility in learners, encouraging them to take ownership of their education. Effective academic task management thus not only increases the frequency and quality of student engagement but also fosters the social and intellectual competencies necessary for lifelong learning. These findings affirm that participation, supported by strategic task management, is a vital contributor to learner growth. Moreover, this finding implies that when teachers effectively manage motivation, classroom environment, and learner participation, it fosters improved developmental outcomes. The learners' ability to build effective study routines, display positive social interaction, and maintain constructive behavior is significantly influenced by how well academic tasks are managed. Educators should thus be encouraged to adopt active and structured approaches to task management as it plays a pivotal role in shaping learners' overall development. The results of the present study indicate a statistically significant relationship between organized and consistent teaching methods and student success. This supports the earlier conclusion of Graham (2019), who emphasized that academic growth is strongly associated with systematic and reliable instructional methods. This study demonstrates that clearly articulated academic expectations contribute to consistent learner development across behavior, social skills, and learning habits. These

results affirm the findings of Washburn (2021), who similarly concluded that well-defined academic standards promote steady and meaningful learner progress. The current investigation revealed that task-oriented facilitation plays a crucial role in the comprehensive development of learners. This supports the work of Gravett (2019), who highlighted the transformative effects of task-centered instructional approaches in enhancing students' overall academic growth.

Table 9. Relationship Between Academic Task Management and Learners' Development

Indicators	Pearson - r	Degree of Correlation	P value
Motivation to learn Classroom environment Learners' participation	0.794	High	0.00
Interpretation	Significant	Decision	Reject

Note: Significance when $P < 0.05$

Through significant correlational data, the current study shows a strong link between effective classroom management strategies and increased learner engagement and outcomes. These findings echo those of Crone et al. (2023), who also identified classroom management as a key factor in promoting learner success. The current study establishes that well-organized instruction enhances learners' motivation, sense of responsibility, and positive behavior. These outcomes are consistent with the insights of Ericsson et al. (2019), who underscored the benefits of structured teaching in improving student motivation and conduct.

3.6. *Domain of Academic Task Management that Significantly Influences the Learners' Development*—Table 10 presents the linear regression analysis, demonstrating the notable impact of academic task management indicators on learners' development. Through linear regression analysis, it was found that the three indicators of academic task management: motivation to learn, classroom environment, and learners' participation are significant predictors of learners' development, with p-values below the 0.05 threshold. Among them, classroom

environment showed the strongest influence ($B = 0.318$, $Beta = 0.049$), suggesting that creating a structured and interactive learning space is pivotal for enhancing student growth. The overall model demonstrates a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.354, signifying that 35.4 percent of the variance in learners' development is accounted for by these indicators. The model demonstrates statistical significance, evidenced by the F-value of 9.453 and a p-value of less than 0.001. The multiple regression model used in Table 10 assesses the influence of three academic task management indicators on learners' development. The model yields an R^2 value of 0.354, indicating that approximately 35.4 percent of the variance in learners' development can be explained by the combined effects of motivation to learn, classroom environment, and learners' participation. The model demonstrates statistical significance, evidenced by an F-value of 9.453 and a p-value below 0.001, indicating that the predictors together exert a substantial influence on the dependent variable. Each of the indicators shows a significant individual contribution to learners' development ($p < 0.05$), leading to the rejection of the respective null

hypotheses. The unstandardized coefficient ($B = 0.263$) for motivation to learn suggests that for every one-unit increase in motivation, there is an expected increase of 0.263 units in learners' development, assuming all other factors are held constant. This positive relationship is further supported by a standardized beta (β) of 0.045, indicating a relatively modest but statistically significant contribution to the model. The standard error of 0.006 is minimal, and the p-value of 0.002 indicates that this relationship is of high significance. This result suggests that as individuals cultivate intrinsic motivation, fueled by their interests, curiosity, or aspirations for success, their overall development shows significant improvement in quantifiable aspects. Students who exhibit strong motivation tend to immerse themselves in academic material, navigate obstacles with resilience, and assume responsibility for their educational journey, leading to beneficial outcomes in both cognitive development and personal growth. Among the three predictors, the classroom environment exhibits the highest unstandardized coefficient ($B = 0.318$), suggesting that a one-unit enhancement in the classroom environment correlates with a 0.318-unit increase in learners' development, while controlling for other variables. The standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.049$) along with a small standard error of 0.005 points to a dependable estimate, while the p-value of 0.001 signifies a highly statistically significant effect. This finding highlights the central role of a well-structured, emotionally supportive, and intellectually stimulating classroom in promoting student development. A positive classroom environment, characterized by clarity, respect, inclusiveness, and effective communication, helps students feel safe, motivated, and connected. These conditions not only facilitate academic learning but also nurture social-emotional skills, resilience, and confidence, making the environment a powerful driver of holistic development. The unstandardized coefficient ($B = 0.287$) for

learners' participation shows that a one-unit increase in participation leads to an expected 0.287-unit increase in learners' development, controlling for other variables. The standardized beta ($\beta = 0.041$) and standard error of 0.007 demonstrate a significant and consistent effect, accompanied by a p-value of 0.004, confirming the rejection of the null hypothesis. Participation denotes the extent to which students are involved in classroom activities, discussions, and collaborative efforts. High participation levels signal that students are not just passive recipients of information but are actively constructing knowledge, sharing ideas, and learning through social interaction. This kind of engagement fosters a wide range of developmental benefits, including communication skills, critical thinking, self-efficacy, and deeper content mastery. Therefore, encouraging participation through effective task design and facilitative teaching strategies is essential for promoting learners' overall development. The results from Table 10 confirm that all three indicators: motivation to learn, classroom environment, and learners' participation are statistically significant predictors of learners' development, with classroom environment exerting the strongest influence, followed by learners' participation and motivation to learn. These findings suggest that enhancing these components through effective academic task management can lead to meaningful improvements in students' holistic development. Educational stakeholders should therefore prioritize structured interventions and practices that simultaneously cultivate motivation, promote a positive learning environment, and engage students actively in their academic journey. These findings imply that teachers' management strategies strongly contribute to students' holistic development, covering cognitive, social, and behavioral domains. Emphasizing classroom environment and structured participation can lead to more meaningful engagement and positive outcomes for learners.

The significance across all indicators reinforces the need for integrated teaching practices that promote motivation, inclusivity, and active participation. Therefore, the null hypotheses are rejected, and the indicators are confirmed to be critical determinants of effective learner development. The current study found that the classroom environment was the strongest predictor of learner growth, as evidenced by the regression analysis. This finding supports the earlier conclusion of Ahmad et al. (2019), who identified the classroom environment as the most influential factor in student development. The alignment between both studies highlights the critical role that physical and emotional learn-

ing spaces play in shaping academic progress. It further emphasizes the need for intentional classroom design to maximize learner outcomes. Findings from this study revealed that learner participation had a significant influence on developmental outcomes. This result confirms the assertion made by Washburn (2021), who identified active participation as a key component of successful learner growth. The current study reinforces the idea that engaging learners in the process not only fosters academic achievement but also enhances behavioral and social skills. This consistency underlines the importance of participatory teaching strategies across diverse educational settings.

Table 10. Analysis on the Indicators of Academic Task Management that Significantly Influence Learners' Development

Model	Task	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decision
H ₀₁	Intercept	-	-	-	-	-
H ₀₂	Motivation to Learn	0.263	0.045	0.006	0.002	Reject H ₀
	Classroom Environment	0.318	0.049	0.005	0.001	Reject H ₀
	Learners' Participation	0.287	0.041	0.007	0.004	Reject H ₀
R²			0.354			
F-value			9.453			
p-value			< 0.001			

Note. Significant at $p < 0.05$. The null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected for Motivation to Learn, Classroom Environment, and Learners' Participation as all have p-values below 0.05.

Motivation emerged in this study as a significant predictor of learner performance, suggesting its foundational role in effective teaching. This supports Graham's (2019) emphasis on motivational design as a core instructional strategy that drives engagement and learning. By aligning with Graham's findings, the present research validates the importance of building lessons around intrinsic and extrinsic motivators. It also underscores the lasting impact of motivation on both cognitive and emotional development in learners. The findings indicate that the arrangement of the classroom environment plays a crucial role in influencing learner auton-

omy and engagement. These findings are consistent with Van Dijk et al. (2020), who linked positive classroom climates with improved learner independence and participation. The correlation observed in the current study affirms the role of environmental factors in cultivating responsible and self-directed learners. It suggests that a well-managed and supportive classroom climate fosters both academic and personal growth. The present study concluded that participatory and motivational strategies are crucial contributors to learners' cognitive and emotional development. This finding supports the work of Muir et al. (2019), who described active en-

engagement as a catalyst for enhancing both intellectual and affective learning domains. The parallels between the studies highlight how intentional engagement techniques can stimulate deeper learning experiences. These insights collectively point to the transformative effect of learner-centered approaches in modern classrooms. The results of the study are strongly supported by Attribution Theory, which explains how individuals interpret the causes of their successes and failures, and how these beliefs influence future behavior. Teachers who possess strong 21st-century attributes, such as a commitment to continuous learning, collaboration, and ethical responsibility that tend to attribute their instructional success to internal, controllable factors like effort and professional growth. This internal attribution fosters greater motivation, reflective practice, and resilience in addressing the challenges of reading instruction. As a result, these teachers are more likely to engage in effective strategies that enhance reading comprehension among students. The influence of these attributes suggests that teachers who believe they can shape their teaching outcomes are more invested in improving their instructional methods. Attribution Theory emphasizes that such beliefs are essential in determining the level of engagement and persistence an individual brings to their professional roles. When teachers view their competence as the result of deliberate choices and continued development, they are more proactive in implementing best practices. Thus, the findings support the idea that a teacher's sense of control and responsibility over their teaching performance plays a crucial role in achieving better literacy outcomes. The findings demonstrate a significant correlation with Social Learning Theory, emphasizing the importance of observation, imitation, and modeling in the learning process. Teachers who demonstrate practical competencies, such as the effective use of technology, innovation in instructional delivery, and adaptability which serve as influential models for students. These observable behaviors not only transmit academic content but also reflect learning strategies that students can emulate. Through modeling adaptive and engaging instruction, teachers foster a classroom culture that promotes active learning and comprehension.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter integrated the main goals of the study and showcased essential statistical results, concluding with pertinent insights and suggestions based on empirical evidence. The study employed a quantitative correlational approach to examine the relationship between academic task management and learners' development among public junior high school teachers in Tagum City Division. Academic task management, operationalized through indicators such as motivation to learn, classroom environment, and learners' participation was found to be consistently implemented at a high level. Notably, the domain of learners' participation emerged as a critical factor in shaping developmental outcomes. Teachers effectively facilitated learners' active involvement in instructional processes, promoting collaboration, responsiveness, and accountability within the classroom setting. The consistently high ratings in this domain reflect a learning environment that values student agency, cooperative engagement, and peer-to-peer interaction in which the key dimensions that contribute to a dynamic and inclusive educational climate.

4.1. Findings—The findings reinforce that paired with strategic academic task management, fosters enhanced learner engagement and a well-structured classroom environment, when

cultivates developmental competencies such as critical thinking, social interaction, and behavioral regulation. Furthermore, the study revealed a significant and positive correlation between effective academic task management and learners' holistic development, with learners' participation serving as a strong predictor of academic and social growth. In essence, nurturing a participative and task-oriented learning environment is essential not only in maximizing learner outcomes but also in reinforcing the teacher's role as a facilitator of growth. Such environments empower students to take ownership of their learning, thereby contributing to sustained academic achievement and a more committed, responsive educational community.

4.2. Conclusions—From the comprehensive analysis of the data collected, the subsequent conclusions have been formulated: Based on the findings of the study, it can be inferred that the educational environment within the Tagum City Division demonstrates a strong level of academic task management, particularly in maintaining a structured classroom setting, nurturing a positive learning climate, and promoting active participation. These elements collectively cultivate a supportive atmosphere that enhances teacher facilitation and encourages meaningful learner engagement. A well-managed classroom environment not only supports learners' academic and social development but also reinforces teachers' professional commitment and satisfaction in performing their instructional roles. On the level of academic task management in terms of motivation to learn, classroom environment, and learners' participation: The findings indicate that academic task management among teachers is generally strong and consistently evident across all three indicators. Teachers are effective in stimulating learners' motivation, establishing structured and inclusive classroom environments, and promoting meaningful participation. These practices contribute to active engagement, learner

attentiveness, and a collaborative learning culture. The consistent ratings across indicators suggest that academic task management is being implemented as a comprehensive strategy that supports learners' educational experiences. On the level of learners' development in terms of study habits, social skills, and behavior: Learners show favorable development across the three measured domains, with particularly strong outcomes in social skills. Teachers play a vital role in facilitating this development through structured interventions, encouragement, and consistent behavioral support. Although all aspects were rated positively, study habits received relatively lower evaluations, indicating the need for more focused guidance on self-management and academic discipline. Overall, learners benefit from an environment that promotes their growth both as individuals and as members of a learning community. On the relationship between academic task management and learners' development: A statistically significant and high positive correlation was found between academic task management and learners' development. This means that the more effectively teachers manage academic tasks through motivation, classroom design, and participation, the greater the learners' growth in study habits, social abilities, and behavior. The correlation supports the idea that task management strategies are integral to facilitating comprehensive learner development. Thus, academic task management is not only a teaching responsibility but also a critical factor in shaping learner success. On which domain of academic task management significantly influences learners' development: Among the three domains, classroom environment emerged as the most influential predictor of learners' development, followed by learners' participation and motivation to learn. This underscores the importance of a well-managed and interactive classroom setting in fostering learners' academic, social, and behavioral competencies. The results emphasize the need for school

systems and teachers to focus on creating supportive, student-centered environments to maximize development. All domains were found to significantly contribute, confirming that each plays a unique role in shaping a holistic educational experience.

4.3. Recommendations—In light of the study’s findings, the subsequent recommendations are presented for consideration: For Teachers – Teachers are encouraged to continue refining their academic task management strategies, particularly in fostering motivation, building interactive classroom environments, and facilitating active learner participation. Greater attention should be given to promoting group study habits and independent work routines to improve learners’ academic discipline. Professional development programs should focus on enhancing skills in classroom design, learner engagement techniques, and individualized instructional support. By doing so, teachers can sustain and even improve the positive developmental outcomes observed among learners. For Learners – Learners are encouraged to take active responsibility for their own development by engaging fully in classroom activities, embracing collaborative work, and practicing effective study habits. They should respond positively to the opportunities provided by teachers to participate and grow in a supportive learning environment. Learners must be guided to recognize the importance of behavior, discipline, and motivation in achieving personal success. Strengthening these internal capacities will support both academic performance and long-term success. For School Administrators – School leaders should prioritize the promotion of structured, inclusive, and engaging

classroom environments across all levels. They are advised to support teaching staff by providing resources, training, and mentoring programs that enhance task management capacity. Administrators should also monitor classroom practices to ensure alignment with the principles of effective task management and learner-centered development. Creating a culture of shared accountability and continuous improvement can further elevate learner outcomes. For the Department of Education (DepEd) – The Department of Education should develop policies and frameworks that institutionalize academic task management as a key competency in teaching standards. Support mechanisms such as in-service training, learning modules, and coaching programs should be designed to help teachers implement evidence-based practices effectively. Furthermore, DepEd should consider regular assessments of academic task management practices and their impact on learners’ development to inform continuous policy enhancement. Ensuring adequate support for creating positive classroom environments should also be a core priority. For Future Researchers – Future studies may explore the long-term impact of academic task management strategies on learner development across different educational levels and contexts. Comparative studies between schools or districts may uncover best practices and regional variations. Additionally, qualitative investigations may provide deeper insight into the specific classroom strategies that are most effective in promoting motivation, participation, and behavioral growth. Future research can also include the learners’ perspectives to gain a more holistic understanding of their developmental needs.

5. References

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